

Hot Corrosion Behavior of $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ -Based Plasma-Sprayed Coating

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Abstract

$\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ (LC) has been identified as a promising thermal barrier coating (TBC) for use up to 1250 °C. In this study, a TBC system was deposited on grit-blasted Inconel 738 using atmospheric plasma spraying (APS) with NiCrAlY as the bond coat, followed by YSZ, and then LC as the top layer. The coatings were exposed to a mixture of molten Na_2SO_4 (45 wt.%) and V_2O_5 (55 wt.%) at 950 °C for hot corrosion. On the top LC layer, LaVO_4 , CeVO_4 and $\text{CeO}_{(1.66-2.00)}$ formed as hot corrosion products after 4 h exposure. A reaction between YSZ and the corrosion products could not be observed due to the absence of YVO_4 . The hot corrosion mechanism of the LC-based TBC is also discussed in this study.

Keywords Thermal barrier coating · $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ · Hot corrosion · High-temperature coating · Yttria-stabilized zirconia

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Introduction

Thermal barrier coatings (TBCs) are commonly used to thermally insulate the structural components of modern gas turbine engines from hot environments and enhance the working temperature, thus improving engine efficiency [1, 2]. Usually, TBCs are processed by atmospheric plasma spraying (APS) due to their rapid production compared with other coating techniques. Conventional TBC ZrO_2 was stabilized with 6–8 wt.% Y_2O_3 (YSZ). It is necessary to increase the combustion temperature, in order to increase the efficiency of engines. However, YSZ material begins to undergo phase transformation and rapid sinter-ability at temperatures much lower than 1200 °C. Hence, an alternative TBC material which works at such high temperatures is required.

More attention has been focused on zirconia doped with elements (such as Y_2O_5 , CeO_2 , Sc_2O_3 , Gd_2O_3 , etc.) [3–5], fluorites [6–9], perovskites [10], and rare-earth zirconates [11]. $\text{Yb}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$, $\text{Sm}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$, $\text{Gd}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$, $\text{La}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$, $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$, etc., are some of the potential candidates in fluorite-based TBC materials [6–9]. Among these fluorite-based TBCs, $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ (LC) possesses excellent thermal insulation, chemical resistance, and phase stability with an optimum mechanical stability [8, 12]. TBCs on structural components are successfully produced by physical vapor deposition and plasma spraying (APS). However, monolithic LC-based TBCs exhibit poor thermal cycling behavior due to the chemical interaction between the LC and Al_2O_3 (thermally grown alumina) over the intermetallic bond coat at elevated temperature. Therefore, the interaction of the underlying Al_2O_3 with the LC is suppressed by the addition of a thermally grown oxide layer (TGO). In view of this, functionally graded ceramic layered (LC and YSZ) TBCs are proposed, which exhibit a lifetime 10 times longer than that of TBCs with monolithic LC layers [13].

When TBCs work in an environment that contains impurities (formed from fuels), such as vanadium, sulfur and sodium, degradation of the coatings occurs due to molten deposits of the salts. Thus, major and critical failure (referred to as hot corrosion) occurs at the operating temperature of the TBCs [14, 15]. During high operating temperatures, vanadate and sulfate salts deposit over the TBCs in a molten state. Later, they react with the top ceramic coating, which ultimately leads to the degradation of TBCs during thermal cycling. Furthermore, the molten salts pass through the top ceramic layer and infiltrate into the underlying bond coat, ultimately leading to failure through oxidation of the bond coat. When conventional TBC and YSZ are exposed to molten V_2O_5 , an excessive volume change occurs due to the interaction between V_2O_5 and Y_2O_3 . This leads to the formation of ZrO_2 (monoclinic) and thus the failure of the coating; spallation by coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) mismatch is associated with the volume change during phase change [16].

ZrO_2 stabilized with highly acidic oxides possesses excellent hot corrosion resistance. Subsequently, the cycling life of YSZ-based TBCs decreases with the doping of trivalent compounds [17]. The defects introduced as a result of doping of trivalent lead to the formation of corrosion salts, and this forms a

sacrificial layer which inhibits further corrosion. It has been demonstrated that Ce_2O_3 -stabilized ZrO_2 possesses superior hot corrosion resistance to YSZ [18]. Co-doping of Y_2O_3 and Ta_2O_5 in ZrO_2 results in potential resistance to molten $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ salt [19, 20]. Dual-layered TBCs with $\text{Gd}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$ and $\text{La}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$ as the top layer on the YSZ layer delayed the effects of hot corrosion by acting as a sacrificial layer [6, 7]. Similarly, the $\text{La}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$ -based TBC has better hot corrosion resistance compared to that of YSZ coatings in the environment of molten V_2O_5 salt [14]. Additionally, early degradation of the YSZ and $\text{La}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$ coatings occurred, while the $\text{La}_2(\text{Zr}_{0.7}\text{Ce}_{0.3})_2\text{O}_7$ coating did not exhibit apparent degradation in the $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ environment at 900 °C [9]. Recently, LCs have been largely considered as effective thermal insulation ceramic layers in TBCs at working temperatures > 1250 °C. However, there is no adequate information on the structural stability and mechanical integrity of LCs in corrosive environments. In the current study, the hot corrosion of atmospheric plasma-sprayed YSZ/LC-TBCs in the vicinity of $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ at 950 °C was studied, and the related mechanisms associated with molten salt infiltration were discussed.

Experimental Procedures

Coating Preparation

Spray-dried 8YSZ (plasma spray grade > 99.5% purity with a particle size of ~ 125 μm) and LC (99.9% purity with a particle size range of – 160 + 325 mesh) were procured from Metco and Beijing Sun Spraying New Materials Co., Ltd. (China), respectively. The morphology of YSZ and LC was spherical and embedded with nano-sized particles. The YSZ/LC-based TBCs were coated on a Ni-based superalloy, Inconel 738 (thickness: 5 mm; diameter: 20 mm), by the atmospheric plasma spraying (APS) method. Prior to coating, the surface of Inconel 738 was grit-blasted using 20 μm Al_2O_3 . Then, an intermetallic NiCrAlY bond coat was coated on the grit-blasted surface using the APS technique with an optimized processing parameter (Table 1). Above the NiCrAlY bond coat, 8YSZ and LC were deposited using the optimized processing parameters, as shown in Table 1; this material is referred to as APS-YSZ | LC (top).

Microstructural and Phase Characterization

The microstructure of the starting powders and the coatings were obtained using a scanning electron microscope (JEOL-JSM 7600F, Tokyo, Japan). The phases in the starting powders and the coatings were analyzed using X-ray diffractometry (XRD; Panalytical Empyrean DY1098, The Netherlands) with Cu as the target and an X-ray wavelength (λ) of 1.5405 Å, and the XRD patterns were recorded for a 2-theta interval of 10–80°.

Table 1 Sample nomenclature, composition, and processing parameters for atmospheric plasma-sprayed YSZ | LC (top) TBCs

Sl. no	Composition	Voltage (V)	Current (A)	H ₂ gas flow rate (SCFH)	Ar gas flow rate (SCFH)	Average powder feed rate (g/min)	Stand-off distance (mm)	Substrate pre-heat (°C)
1	NiCrAlY	60	500	10	110	15	120	180
2	8YSZ	57.4	690	15	80	15	100	200
3	LC	57.0	668	15	80	15	100	200

SCFH standard cubic feet per hour

Hot Corrosion Testing

The APS-YSZ | LC (top) TBCs were subjected to hot corrosion testing in a V_2O_5/Na_2SO_4 composite mixture at a weight ratio of 55:45 at an isothermal temperature of 950 °C for 4 h. The salt mixture was applied uniformly on the surface of the APS-YSZ | LC (top) at a concentration of $\sim 25 \text{ mg/cm}^2$. After isothermal heating at 950 °C for 4 h, the samples were furnace cooled to ambient temperature and subjected to microstructural and phase analysis.

Results and Discussion

The morphology of the bond coat (NiCrAlY) and ceramic top coats (APS-YSZ | LC) obtained using atmospheric plasma spraying is shown in Fig. 1a–d. The morphology of the bond coat (Fig. 1a, b) confirmed complete splat formation with high roughness. The surface morphology of APS-YSZ | LC (Fig. 1c, d) shows a relatively smooth surface with sphere-shaped LC particles dispersed on the surface. This finding validated the complete melting and solidification of the LC. The cross-sectional micrograph of the plasma-sprayed APS-YSZ | LC (top) coating confirms that the coatings are well adhered to Inconel 738, as shown in Fig. 2. The boundaries of the NiCrAlY, YSZ, and LC coatings on the substrate are clearly distinguished.

Fig. 1 Surface morphology of the a & b NiCrAlY and c & d APS-YSZ | LC coatings

Fig. 2 Elemental mapping of the cross-sectional microstructure of the APS-YSZ | LC coating

Furthermore, elemental mapping via EDS clearly revealed the distribution of the constituents in the coating.

The average thicknesses of the individual layers were about 99.0, 183.8 and 200.4 μm for the NiCrAlY, YSZ and LC layers, respectively. The thickness of the individual layer was achieved with one coating pass for NiCrAlY and two passes for YSZ and LC with a powder feed rate of 15 g/min. Additionally, these individual layers exhibited different levels of porosity.

Phase analysis of the APS-YSZ | LC (top) coating after hot corrosion at 950 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 45 wt. % Na_2SO_4 and 55 wt.% V_2O_5 for 4 h is shown in Fig. 3. The peaks in the

Fig. 3 X-ray diffraction pattern of hot corrosion tested APS-YSZ | LC (top) coatings and hot corrosion debris (formed due to spallation during hot corrosion)

Table 2 Phase quantification of the hot-corroded YSZ | LC (top) TBCs

Sl. no	Hot corrosion product	Phase (vol.%) in	
		Retained coating	Debris (due to spallation during HC)
1	LaVO ₄	19.6	25.2
2	CeVO ₄	02.0	0
3	SO ₄	49.1	0
4	CeO _(1.66–2.00)	29.3	74.8

APS-YSZ | LC (top)**Fig. 4** a–c Surface morphology of the hot-corroded APS-YSZ | LC (top) coating

XRD pattern confirm the reaction of corrosive salts with the top layer (LC) of the APS coatings. The LC layer reacts with the corrosive salt and forms by-products (LaVO₄, CeVO₄ and CeO_(1.66–2.00)). Additionally, the stresses accumulate on the LC layer during hot corrosion, leading to spallation of the coating. The XRD pattern of the debris that formed due to spallation (Fig. 3) confirmed the dissociation of LC into LaVO₄, CeVO₄ and CeO_(1.66–2.00). Furthermore, the XRD pattern obtained from the top surface of the APS-YSZ | LC (top) coating after blowing away the debris that formed during the hot corrosion test confirms the presence of additional phases on top of the phases present in the debris. An extra phase, SO₄, was found on the top surface, where spallation occurred. This difference is attributed to the SO₄ phases at the interface during the dissociation of NaSO₄ + V₂O₅ increasing the stresses that lead to failure (coating spallation). Moreover, peaks corresponding to YSZ- or YSZ-related corrosion products (mainly YVO₄) are not identified either at the coating surface or in the debris. This confirms that only a small fraction of the APS-YSZ | LC (top) coating interacts with the corrosive salts, and the remaining part of the top LC layer still adheres well to the underlying YSZ layer. This result confirmed the structural stability of the YSZ and LC interfaces after the hot corrosion test. The identified phases and the quantification (using XRD) are tabulated in Table 2.

Some new peaks appeared in the hot-corroded coatings that indicate the presence of LaVO₄, CeVO₄ and CeO_(x). Additionally, no peaks corresponding to LC were detected in the APS coating or debris (after hot corrosion). This implies that the corrosion by-products are thick enough to cover the underlying part of the LC layer. The contact surface consists of uniformly distributed hot corrosion

products (Fig. 4a–c), which exhibit cuboidal and particle-shaped morphologies. The elemental content on the surface of the hot-corroded APS-YSZ | LC (top) coatings was measured via EDS (Fig. 5), and the results are listed in Table 2. Elemental analysis (EDS) and phase analysis (XRD) confirmed the presence of the CeO_2 phase.

The XRD pattern (Fig. 3) confirmed that the phases were LaVO_4 and CeVO_4 , which can be identified as the $(\text{La}, \text{Ce})\text{VO}_4$ phase. Furthermore, the melting temperatures of V_2O_5 and Na_2SO_4 are $\sim 885^\circ\text{C}$ and $\sim 689^\circ\text{C}$, respectively, which are lower than the hot corrosion testing temperature (950°C).

In the corrosion salt mixture, the development of vanadate and NaVO_3 at temperatures above 610°C (melting temperature) is expressed as follows:

The liquid NaVO_3 phase reacts with the top layer of the TBC ($\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$) and produces rare-earth vanadates (LaVO_4 and CeVO_4) and CeO_2 . Subsequently, the following reaction will be active

The hot corrosion of YSZ | LC (top) TBCs in the presence of molten $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5 + \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4$ salt is most likely the result of the interaction between these compounds. This interaction forms the intermediate by-product NaVO_3 , which diffuses through the coating. Subsequently, NaVO_3 interacts with $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ to form LaVO_4 , CeVO_4 and $\text{CeO}_{(1.66-2.00)}$. During hot corrosion, evaporation of $\text{Na}+$ occurs. Later, V_2O_5 reacts with LC and CeO_2 to form LaVO_4 and CeVO_4 . The formation of CeVO_4 is limited as a result of limited corrosion duration.

Phase analysis and SEM show that the corrosive by-products of APS-YSZ | LC (top) in molten corrosive salts are CeVO_4 and LaVO_4 . The reaction between the molten hot-corrosion salts and LCs involves the Lewis acid–base mechanism [9]. This is due to the comparable basicity of La_2O_3 and CeO_2 ; additionally, the La_2O_3 and CeO_2 in the LC react with V_2O_5 simultaneously.

Fig. 5 Elemental distribution in the hot-corroded surface of the APS-YSZ | LC (top) coating

Conclusion

The hot corrosion characteristics of atmospheric plasma-sprayed YSZ | LC (top) TBCs exposed to the molten salt $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ were investigated. During the exposure of molten $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ salt for 4 h at 950 °C, LaVO_4 , CeVO_4 and CeO_2 were formed at the surface of the TBC by the interaction between $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ and the molten salt (V_2O_5). As the hot corrosion proceeded, Na_2SO_4 decomposed to SO_4 due to the evaporation of Na+ and was found at the top of the TBCs. After the hot corrosion tests, the monoclinic ZrO_2 and (La, Ce) VO_4 crystals are formed as a by-product in YSZ | LC (top) coating. Furthermore, V_2O_5 reacts with $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ to form a certain amount of CeVO_4 and LaVO_4 . As a result, permeable layers of (La, Ce) VO_4 and $\text{CeO}_{(1.66-2.00)}$ formed after isothermal holding for 4 h at 950 °C. With the V_2O_5 salt, the corrosive product (Ce, La) VO_4 was formed due to the direct interaction between the $\text{La}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{O}_7$ and V_2O_5 solid solution in the molten state.

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Author Contributions AS prepared the LC-YSZ composites and $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-Na}_2\text{SO}_4$ salt mixture, analyzed the results, and wrote the manuscript; MP performed the SEM, EDS, and XRD analyses of the powders and coatings. PS prepared the LC-YSZ composite coating. PR performed the SEM and EDS analyses, RM contributed to the hot corrosion studies, AS revised the manuscript, AK provided facilities for coating deposition, and AP conceived the study, supervised the project, revised the manuscript, and provided research guidelines. All the contributors have read and subsequently agreed to publish the manuscript.

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Declarations

Conflict of interest The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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References

1. A. H. Pakseresht, M. R. Rahimpour, M. Alizadeh, S. M. M. Hadavi, and A. Shahbazkhan, in *Research Perspectives on Functional Micro-and Nanoscale Coatings*, (IGI Global, 2016), p. 396.

2. S. Ariharan, R. Hassan, A. Bhadauria, A. Tiwari, R. Tandon, Keshri AK, et al., *Fundamentals of Thermal Spraying*, CRC Press, 2022.
3. L. Sun, H. Guo, H. Peng, S. Gong, and H. Xu, *Ceramics International* 39, 3447 (2013).
4. S. Ariharan, A. Gupta, A. Keshri, A. Agarwal, and K. Balani, *Nanoscience and Nanotechnology Letters* 4, 323 (2013).
5. S. Ariharan, B. Wangaskar, V. Xavier, T. Venkateswaran, and K. Balani, *Ceramics International* 45, 18951 (2019).
6. Y. Ozgurluk, K. M. Doleker, and A. C. Karaoglanli, *Applied Surface Science* 438, 96 (2018).
7. Y. Ozgurluk, K. M. Doleker, H. Ahlatci, and A. C. Karaoglanli, *Surface and Coatings Technology* 411, 126969 (2021).
8. I. Parchovianská, M. Parchovianský, A. Nowicka, A. Prnová, P. Švančárek, and A. Pakseresht, *Journal of Materials Research and Technology* 24, 4573 (2023).
9. X. Wang, L. Guo, H. Peng, L. Zheng, H. Guo, and S. Gong, *Ceramics International* 41, 6604 (2015).
10. L. Guo, H. Guo, G. Ma, M. Abbas, and S. Gong, *Ceramics International* 38, 4345 (2012).
11. Y. Zhang, L. Guo, X. Zhao, and F. Ye, *Materials Letters* 136, 157 (2014).
12. X. Cao, R. Vassen, W. Fischer, F. Tietz, W. Jungen, and D. Stöver, *Advanced Materials* 15, 1438 (2003).
13. W. Ma, S. Gong, H. Li, and H. Xu, *Surface and Coatings Technology* 202, 2704 (2008).
14. B. R. Marple, J. Voyer, M. Thibodeau, D. R. Nagy, and R. Vassen, (2006).
15. K. L. Luthra and H. S. Spacil, *Journal of Electrochemical Society* 129, 649 (1982).
16. W. Hertl, *Journal of Applied Physics* 63, 5514 (1988).
17. F. M. Pitek and C. G. Levi, *Surface and Coatings Technology* 201, 6044 (2007).
18. S. Y. Park, J. H. Kim, M. C. Kim, H. S. Song, and C. G. Park, *Surface and Coatings Technology* 190, 357 (2005).
19. M. H. Habibi, L. Wang, J. Liang, and S. M. Guo, *Corrosion Science* 75, 409 (2013).
20. S. Raghavan, H. Wang, R. B. Dinwiddie, W. D. Porter, R. Vaßen, D. Stöver, et al., *Journal of American Ceramic Society* 87, 431 (2004).

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